

Table 1. Rice hispa beetle feeding and development on some common weeds. BRRI, Gazipur, Bangladesh, 1985.

Host	Feeding damage ^a	Eggs deposited	Grub development (%)
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	3	Few	0
<i>Digitaria ciliaris</i>	9	Few	0
<i>Digitaria setigera</i>	9	Few	0
<i>Echinochloa colona</i>	9	Few	0
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	9	Few	0
<i>Eleusine indica</i>	9	Few	0
<i>Leersia hexandra</i>	9	Few	0
Rice (BR3)	9	Many	>50%

^a 0 to 9 scale: 0 = no damage, 9 = more than 50% leaves damaged.

Seven weed species and rice variety BR3 (30-d-old plants) were grown in 15-cm clay pots. Each pot was infested with 4 greenhouse-reared, mated, hispa females and enclosed in mylar film cages for 7 d. Exposed plants were sprinkled with water daily for grub development. Feeding damage was graded on a 0 to 9 scale.

The beetles laid numerous eggs on rice, but few on weeds (Table 1). Grubs died at the 1st- or 2d-instar stage on weeds, but more than 50% developed into pupae on rice. Feeding damage on

Cyperus rotundus was minimal (damage grade 3) and no grubs developed. All other weeds and rice were heavily damaged.

It appears that, while rice hispa may use weeds as alternate food sources, it cannot complete its life cycle on them.

In a separate experiment, 30-d-old plants of rice (BR3), wheat (Barkat), maize (JC-2), and 9 species of weeds were grown separately in 15-cm clay pots enclosed in fine mesh wire net rectangular cages, with 4 replications. Greenhouse-reared hispa beetles were

Table 2. Preference of rice hispa beetles for rice, wheat, maize, and some common weeds. BRRI, Gazipur, Bangladesh, 1986.

Host	Beetles settling on plants (%)
Rice (BR3)	24.2 a
<i>Echinochloa colona</i>	19.2 ab
<i>Eleusine indica</i>	14.2 bc
<i>Scirpus maritimus</i>	9.0 cd
<i>Digitaria ciliaris</i>	8.3 d
<i>Leersia hexandra</i>	8.0 d
<i>Paspalum distichum</i>	7.2 d
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i>	2.7 e
Maize (JC-2)	2.7 e
<i>Commelina benghalensis</i>	2.4 e
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	1.3 e
Wheat (Barkat)	0.7 e

starved for 3 h and released at 100 beetles/cage. Beetles that settled on plants were counted 48 h after infestation.

Rice was the most preferred site (24% beetles settled), followed by *Echinochloa colona* (19%) and *Eleusine indica* (14%) (Table 2). Wheat was least preferred. Hispa beetles probably disperse to other plants when the available rice canopy is inadequate to support their numbers. □

Effect of parasitization on food consumption of rice leaffolder (LF) *Marasmia patnalis*

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The amount of food the LF, an important defoliator of the rice plant, consumes during feeding affects yields. But when LF is parasitized, the amount of leaf tissue consumed changes.

LF parasitoids are abundant in ricefields. *Copidomopsis nacoletiae*, a parasitoid of egg and larvae, and *Goniozus triangulifer*, a parasitoid of LF larvae, are important mortality factors for LF in the Philippines.

We studied the influence of parasitism by *C. nacoletiae* on LF food consumption. Ten newly laid LF eggs were exposed for 24 h in tubes containing colonies of the parasitoid.

The hatch was reared individually in tubes with cut leaves from 60-d-old rice variety IR64. Leaves were changed every 24 h until LF larvae ceased feeding and mummified. The area of leaf consumed was measured on graph paper.

In another experiment, 20 newly hatched LF larvae were reared individually in tubes with cut leaves of rice variety IR64. Leaves were changed daily. When the larvae reached the 4th instar, 10 were placed individually in tubes containing pairs of *G. triangulifer*. After parasitization, the larvae were returned to their original tube containing cut rice leaf until they stopped feeding.

The leaf area consumed was measured on graph paper. LF parasitized by *C. nacoletiae* consumed more food than unparasitized LF. The lowest food consumption was by larvae parasitized by *G. triangulifer* (see figure). *C. nacoletiae*-parasitized larvae fed for 16.4

d; *G. triangulifer*-parasitized larvae fed 13.9 d; and unparasitized larvae fed 15.2 d.

The number of live larvae and the percentage of damaged leaves are the bases for deciding to spray LF with insecticide. Presence or absence of either parasitoid might influence an integrated control program. □

Influence of parasitization by *C. nacoletiae* and *G. triangulifer* on leaf consumption by LF.